

Perception of Skill Development for Effective Instructional Delivery in Social Studies among Upper Basic Teachers in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Upper basic teachers in Niger State, Nigeria. Grounded in Human Capital Theory and Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC), the research explores the importance of ongoing professional development in enhancing teachers' competencies, given the evolving demands of modern education. A descriptive survey design was employed and the population of the study consist of all upper basic social studies teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Niger state; a sample size of 153 teachers were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled: (PSDFEIDSOSUBT), experts were sought to confirm the instrument's validity and a pilot project was conducted to ascertain its reliability. The results were analyzed through descriptive statistics and a one-sample t-test. The findings reveal that while teachers recognize the value of skill development, there is a significant concern about the adequacy and effectiveness of current resources and training programs. The cumulative mean score of 3.27 indicates a generally positive perception of skill development, but gaps remain in meeting the specific needs of Social Studies teachers. The study underscores the need for more targeted and adequately resourced professional development initiatives to ensure that teachers are well-equipped to deliver effective instruction. The variability in perceptions suggests disparities in access to quality development opportunities, pointing to the necessity for systemic improvements in educational support. This research highlights the critical role of skill development in enhancing instructional delivery and improving educational outcomes in Social Studies, with broader implications for educational policy and practice in Nigeria.

Keyword: Skill, teachers, perception, Studies, Niger

Introduction

The quality of education is heavily influenced by the skills and competencies of teachers, particularly in foundational subjects such as Social Studies. Sharma and Poorva (2023) pronounced that skill development stands as an essential pillar upon which individual progress and societal advancement rest. Skill development is a powerful catalyst for economic growth, social mobility, and the reduction of income inequality. In today's world, grasping the complexities of skill development along with the opportunities it presents and the challenges it poses is not just a personal pursuit. It is a global necessity. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping a more equitable and prosperous future. Social Studies forms a critical component of the curriculum at the Upper Basic level, where it serves as a conduit for imparting essential civic, moral, and social knowledge. However, the effectiveness of instructional delivery in this subject is closely tied to the ongoing professional development and skill enhancement of the teachers responsible for it. According to Saini and Chourasiya (2023) continuous learning and up-skilling are crucial for enhancing teacher's effective delivery of instruction for employability in today's fast-changing job market where technology is the driving force. The unprecedented pace of technological innovation, the globalization of economies, and the shifting nature of work have propelled the acquisition and refinement of skills to the forefront of both personal and collective aspirations (Sharma & Poorva, 2023). In a study by Akinbote (2010) on teaching Social Studies in Nigeria's colleges of education: The challenges and prospects; findings showed that Social Studies teachers who participated in regular professional development programs demonstrated significantly higher levels of instructional competence compared to those who did not. Moreover, teachers who engaged in collaborative learning communities reported greater confidence in their ability to deliver complex Social Studies content, such as human rights and democratic governance. Similarly, Olojube, Egbezor and Kpolovie (2012) in a study on teacher's professional development and quality assurance in Nigerian secondary schools found out that teachers who perceived their skills as inadequate were more likely to struggle with delivering content effectively, leading to lower student achievement in Social Studies.

The ongoing professional development and skill enhancement of Social Studies teachers are not merely optional but essential components in ensuring the quality of education at the Upper Basic level. As the demands of the modern world continue to evolve, so too must the skills and competencies of educators. Teachers who are equipped with the latest pedagogical strategies and who continuously refine their instructional techniques are better positioned to deliver engaging and effective lessons. This, in turn, nurtures a more informed, responsible, and capable student body, prepared to navigate the complexities of contemporary society. As the evidence from various studies suggests, investment in teacher development is an investment in the future, one that holds the promise of greater educational outcomes, social cohesion, and economic progress. Therefore, prioritizing the professional growth of Social Studies teachers is not just a matter of educational policy, but a crucial step toward building a more equitable and prosperous society.

Despite the recognized importance of skill development in enhancing instructional delivery, many Social Studies teachers at the Upper Basic level in Niger State, Nigeria, continue to face significant challenges. While ongoing professional development is crucial for keeping educators abreast of modern pedagogical strategies, there is growing concern that existing programs and resources are insufficient to meet the unique needs of Social Studies teachers. This inadequacy not only hampers their ability to deliver complex and interdisciplinary content effectively but also contributes to a sense of being underprepared and unsupported in their teaching roles. Consequently, this may lead to diminished student engagement and lower educational outcomes in a subject critical for fostering civic knowledge and social responsibility.

The problem, therefore, is to investigate the perceptions of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers in Niger State for the effectiveness and adequacy of skill development programs and resources in enhancing their instructional delivery. Understanding these perceptions is essential for identifying gaps in the current professional development framework and for proposing strategies to improve the support provided to Social Studies educators, ultimately leading to better teaching practices and improved student learning experiences.

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the question below:

1. What is the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The research hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria

Theoretical framework

This study adopted the Human Capital Theory and Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC) to explain upper basic social studies teachers' perceptions of skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria:

Human Capital Theory: The theory was propounded by Becker (1964) it posits that investments in education, training, and health enhance an individual's productivity, which in turn increases their economic value or income potential. It views education and skills as forms of capital, akin to physical assets, that contribute to economic growth and personal income. The theory emphasizes that spending on education and training is a form of investment in human capital, leading to better economic outcomes for individuals and societies.

Skill-Biased Technological Change (SBTC): Authored by Katz & Krueger (1998) the theory argues that technological advancements, particularly in information and communication technology, have increased the demand for skilled labor while reducing the demand for less-skilled labor. This leads to wage disparities, with higher wages for skilled workers who can effectively use new technologies, and stagnant or declining wages for less-skilled workers. The theory helps explain the growing wage inequality observed in many economies, particularly since the late 20th century.

Application of Skill-Biased Technological Change and Human Capital theories to instructional delivery

The application of Human Capital Theory and SBTC Theory provides a comprehensive understanding of why Upper Basic Social Studies teachers in Niger State perceive skill development as essential for effective instructional delivery. Human Capital Theory underscores the value of skill acquisition as an investment in their professional growth, while SBTC Theory highlights the necessity of skill development in keeping pace with technological changes that impact educational practices. Together, these theories illustrate the critical role that skill development plays in enhancing instructional delivery and ultimately improving educational outcomes in Niger state and beyond.

Conceptual Issues

Perception: Perception is a multifaceted mental process that entails the interpretation and comprehension of sensory information from the environment. According to Schacter, Gilbert, Wegner and Matthew (2011) perception involves selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory inputs to construct a coherent and meaningful representation of the world. This process is influenced by past experiences, expectations, and cultural background, as highlighted by Omolayo (2018). Nwachukwu (2017) further emphasizes that perception is the way individuals interpret and make sense of their surroundings, integrating their senses, emotions, and prior experiences.

Deduced from these definitions, we can define perception as the cognitive process by which individuals actively construct an understanding of the world by selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory stimuli in the context of their prior knowledge, experiences, and socio-cultural background.

Skill development: Skill development is a process of identifying gaps in one's abilities and addressing them by developing, improving, and rejuvenating relevant skills needed to excel and enhance the quality of results in an assigned job. Reddy and Pujar (2021) describe this process as one that increases an individual's ability to execute tasks effectively, regardless of the domain or situation. Additionally, skill development involves acquiring new skills or enhancing existing ones to improve performance and increase capabilities in specific areas. This process can include formal education, training programs, on-the-job learning, or self-directed study. Skill development is essential for personal and professional growth, as it enables individuals to adapt to evolving job markets, enhance productivity, and pursue career advancement. It encompasses various types of skills, including technical, soft (interpersonal), cognitive, and vocational skills.

In this regard, skill development can be defined as the systematic process of acquiring, enhancing, and refining skills to improve competence and performance in specific areas. This process involves continuous learning and adaptation to meet the demands of dynamic environments, ensuring individuals remain competitive and capable of achieving their professional and personal goals.

Instructional delivery: Delivery of instruction refers to the methods and techniques employed by teachers to convey information to students and foster learning. According to Ertmer and Newby (2013), it encompasses the strategies and approaches teachers use to promote student understanding and engagement. Hattie (2015) expands on this by noting that the delivery of instruction involves not only the presentation of information but also the application of various instructional strategies and techniques, alongside the quality of teacher-student interactions. Gagné, Briggs, and Wager (1992) further define delivery of instruction as the process of transferring knowledge from the instructor to the student, emphasizing the importance of selecting appropriate instructional materials and methods, and presenting them in a clear and effective manner. Instructional delivery involves employing a spectrum of methods, techniques, and strategies to impart knowledge, nurturing skill acquisition, and competencies across diverse educational and organizational contexts (Smith et al., 2022; Johnson & Smith, 2023; Brown & Garcia, 2024).

Thus, delivery of instruction is the systematic approach by which teachers convey knowledge and skills to learners, utilizing a combination of instructional strategies, materials, and methods to facilitate understanding and retention. This definition highlights the deliberate and organized nature of instructional delivery, emphasizing the importance of clarity, interaction, and the thoughtful selection of teaching tools.

In the changing educational landscape, teachers play a crucial role in shaping students' futures. For Social Studies in Niger State, Nigeria, teacher skills and competencies are vital for effective instruction. Understanding how Social Studies teachers perceive their skill development is key to improving instructional quality. This literature review examines research on teacher perceptions of skill development and its impact on instructional practices and student outcomes in Upper Basic Social Studies in Niger State, Nigeria.

Teacher Professional Development and Instructional Delivery: Teacher professional development is a cornerstone of educational quality, particularly in disciplines such as Social Studies, which are integral to students' understanding of societal structures. As Aparicio-Molina and Sepúlveda-López (2023) emphasize, the professional growth of teachers necessitates not only the provision of structured opportunities and practices that foster such development but also the recognition of the existing

competencies and evolving capabilities of educators. Continuous professional development is widely acknowledged as essential for equipping teachers with the pedagogical skills necessary to enhance student learning outcomes. Desimone, Porter, Garet, Yoon, and Birman (2002) argue that effective professional development is characterized by a focus on content, active learning opportunities, and sustained engagement, all of which contribute to improved instructional practices. For Social Studies teachers, such professional development is critical, given the interdisciplinary nature of the subject, which encompasses history, geography, economics, and civics (Garet, Porter, Desimone, Birman & Yoon, 2001). This multifaceted content necessitates a deep and continually updated knowledge base, underscoring the importance of ongoing professional development.

Perception of Skill Development among Teachers: Teachers' perceptions of their professional skills significantly influence their approach to instructional responsibilities. Avalos (2011) posits that when teachers feel confident in their skills and believe they have access to adequate resources, they are more likely to demonstrate efficacy and confidence in their teaching. This perception of competence is crucial, as it directly impacts their motivation and teaching strategies, thereby affecting student engagement and learning outcomes. Borko (2004) observed that teachers' perceptions of their professional competencies have a direct bearing on their instructional strategies and the level of student engagement. In the context of Social Studies, where the content is often broad and abstract, teachers' confidence in their instructional skills is particularly critical. The ability to navigate and effectively communicate complex, interdisciplinary content is contingent upon teachers' self-perception of their skills, which in turn affects their instructional delivery.

Challenges in Skill Development for Social Studies Teachers: The skill development of Social Studies teachers in Nigeria faces significant challenges, reflective of broader systemic issues within the educational framework. The Nigerian education system is frequently criticized for its overly theoretical approach, with insufficient emphasis on practical skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Ogunyemi, 2011). These challenges are particularly pronounced for Social Studies teachers, who must constantly update their knowledge and skills to address the evolving nature of the subject, which now includes contemporary issues such as global citizenship, digital literacy, and environmental education. According to Ogunyemi (2011), inadequate access to professional development opportunities, limited resources, and insufficient support from educational authorities are key barriers to effective service delivery among Social Studies teachers. Saini (2023) further identifies systemic issues such as inadequate funding for education and skills development and the lack of relevance of current educational practices to contemporary needs as major obstacles to skill development. Ehindero (2014) adds that many teachers feel unprepared to effectively teach new content areas, which hinders effective instructional delivery.

Impact of Skill Development on Instructional Delivery: In an era increasingly characterized by automation and artificial intelligence, the traditional roles of teachers are evolving, necessitating a focus on skill development that aligns with these changes. The impact of skill development on instructional delivery, particularly in Social Studies, cannot be overstated. Knight (2009) highlights that teachers who engage in targeted professional development, particularly in areas such as inquiry-based learning, critical thinking, and the integration of digital tools, are better equipped to engage students and foster a deeper understanding of complex subject matter. This is particularly relevant in Social Studies, where the ability to critically analyze and discuss diverse issues is paramount. Darling-Hammond, Wei, Andree, Richardson, and Orphanos (2009) argue that professional development that emphasizes practical application and aligns with curriculum standards significantly improves instructional strategies and, consequently, student outcomes. This alignment ensures that teachers are not only knowledgeable about the content but are also adept at employing instructional strategies that promote critical thinking and active student engagement.

The interconnection between teacher professional development, skill development, and instructional delivery in Social Studies is evident. The challenges faced by Social Studies teachers in Nigeria, including those in Niger State, highlight the need for a more practical and supportive approach to professional development. Addressing these challenges through targeted, content-focused, and sustained professional development can significantly enhance instructional delivery, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes in Social Studies education.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design to examine the perceptions of Social Studies teachers in Upper Basic Schools across Niger State. The target population comprised 767 Social Studies teachers from 229 schools, with a sample size of 153 teachers (20% of the population) selected from 36 schools across 9 local government areas through stratified and simple random sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled; (PSDFEIDSOSUBT), validated by experts in Social Studies and test and measurement. To ensure reliability, a pilot test was conducted with 40 teachers from Bosso Local Government Area, who were not included in the main study but shared similar characteristics with the participants. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient obtained was .827, deemed adequate for the study. Descriptive statistics, including

frequency counts and percentages, were used to analyze participants' demographics, while mean and standard deviation addressed the research questions. One-sample t-test was employed to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level.

Presentation of Bio Data Variable

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Male	101	68.2
Female	47	31.8
Total	148	100

Source: Researchers field work (2024)

A total of 101 representing 68.2% of the respondents are male and the rest 47 representing 31.8% are female respondent

Answering of Research questions

What is the perception of Upper basic Social Studies teachers' on skill development for effective instructional delivery in Niger state, Nigeria?

Table 2: On perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development for instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	I feel that training programs have significantly enhanced the teacher's teaching skills.	36	79	15	18	2.90	0.91
2	Additional training if undertaken can improve the confidence of Social Studies teachers.	44	83	7	14	3.06	0.85
3	The resources provided for skill development are valuable and effective to the teaching and learning of Social Studies.	111	25	9	3	3.65	0.69
4	The opportunities for skill enhancement are well-tailored to meet the needs of Social Studies teachers.	66	54	17	11	3.18	0.91
5	My skills have improved significantly due to ongoing professional development programs.	90	39	14	5	3.45	0.80
6	The support systems in place have contributed immensely to my skill advancement.	71	46	31	0	3.27	0.79
7	I feel that the available skill development programs are inadequate for my needs.	88	52	7	1	3.53	0.62
8	The resources provided for skill development have been insufficient and ineffective.	101	33	4	10	3.52	0.84
9	I feel ill-equipped and unprepared to teach Upper Basic Social Studies despite available skill development programs.	43	81	19	5	3.09	0.74
10	The training sessions I've attended did not contribute significantly to my skill enhancement.	55	69	2	22	3.06	0.99
Cumulative						3.27	0.81

Decision Mean = 2.50

The perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria, is very high especially as the cumulative mean of 3.27 is above the 2.50 decision mean. Specifically, most asserted that feel that the available skill development programs are inadequate for my needs. With a mean of 3.53 and the resources provided for skill development have been insufficient and ineffective. With the second highest mean of 3.52

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development for instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria.

Table 3: One sample t-test statistic on the Perception of Upper Basic Social Studies Teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	Std.	Mean diff	Df	T computed	T-critical	P
hypo ¹	148	3.5000	4.03640	30.50	147	91.926	1.96	0.011

P = 0.011 < 0.05, t computed = 91.92 > 1.96 at df 147

Outcome of the one sample t test statistics revealed that significant difference exists in the perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria Reason being that the p value of 0.011 is below the 0.05 and it's computed t value of 91.026 is above the 1.96 t critical at df 147. The mean difference was put at 30.50. The null hypothesis that state that there is no significant difference in the perception of Upper Basic Social Studies teachers on skills development towards instructional delivery in Niger State, Nigeria is hereby rejected

Presentation of Results

Findings of the study revealed that teachers believe providing resources for skill development would significantly enhance the effectiveness of Social Studies teaching and learning. They also recognized the positive impact of existing support systems on their professional growth. However, teachers perceived the current resources allocated for skill development in instructional delivery as inadequate and ineffective.

Discussion of Results

The study provides a nuanced understanding of the perceptions held by Upper Basic Social Studies teachers in Niger State, Nigeria, regarding skill development for instructional delivery. The findings reveal a complex landscape where teachers recognize the importance of skill development yet express concerns about the adequacy of current resources and support systems. This discussion synthesizes the key findings with relevant literature to offer insights into the implications for educational practice and policy.

Perception of Skill Development: The results indicate that the majority of teachers perceive skill development as crucial for effective instructional delivery, aligning with the Human Capital Theory's assertion that investments in education and training enhance professional competence and productivity (Becker, 1964). The cumulative mean of 3.27 suggests a generally positive perception of skill development among teachers, indicating a recognition of its value in enhancing teaching efficacy and student outcomes. This finding is consistent with Avalos (2011), who emphasized that teachers' confidence in their skills directly impacts their instructional practices and, subsequently, student engagement.

However, the perception that the available skill development programs are inadequate and the resources provided are insufficient and ineffective is particularly concerning. With mean scores of 3.53 and 3.52, respectively, these findings suggest significant gaps between teachers' needs and the support provided by the educational system. This aligns with Ogunyemi (2011), who critiqued the Nigerian educational framework for its theoretical approach and insufficient emphasis on practical skills development. The inadequacy of resources and support systems, as highlighted by the teachers, may contribute to a sense of being ill-equipped and unprepared to meet the demands of their instructional roles.

Impact of Professional Development on Instructional Delivery: The study further reveals that ongoing professional development programs have positively influenced teachers' skills, with a mean score of 3.45 indicating a significant improvement in instructional capabilities. This is supported by Knight (2009), who argued that targeted professional development, particularly in areas such as critical thinking and digital tool integration, enhances instructional delivery. The findings underscore the importance of continuous professional development that is aligned with the evolving demands of the educational landscape, particularly in interdisciplinary subjects like Social Studies, where teachers must navigate complex and diverse content areas.

Despite these positive perceptions, the significant difference in teachers' perceptions of skill development, as revealed by the one-sample t-test ($p = 0.011 < 0.05$), suggests variability in how these programs are experienced across different contexts. This variability could be attributed to disparities in access to quality professional development opportunities and resources, a point highlighted by Saini (2023), who identified systemic issues such as inadequate funding and the irrelevance of current educational practices as major obstacles to skill development in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The study's findings underscore the importance of skill development for effective instructional delivery in Social Studies, while also highlighting significant gaps in the resources and support provided to teachers in Niger State, Nigeria. Addressing these gaps through targeted professional development and better resource allocation is essential for empowering teachers to deliver high-quality education that meets the needs of their students in an increasingly complex and dynamic world.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations:
Develop comprehensive, targeted professional development programs specifically for Social Studies teachers. Focus on practical training in critical thinking, digital literacy, and interdisciplinary strategies. Offer regular workshops, seminars, and continuous learning opportunities to help teachers adapt to evolving educational demands. Additionally, increase government resource allocation for teacher skill development

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to Prof. Sadiq Mohammed of the Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, for his invaluable guidance and mentorship throughout this work. His unwavering support and profound insights have greatly contributed to its success. I am also deeply indebted to Mallam Ismail Babangida, a master's degree candidate in the same department, for his positive contributions and assistance, which were instrumental in shaping this research. Their dedication and expertise have been truly inspiring, and I remain immensely grateful for their support

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